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If you are looking for new shoes and sandals to wear for the spring and summer, you are in luck. We have looked and put together a list of the latest styles in shoes. Many of your favorite stores, designers and online web sites should carry these types of shoes, so if you see a style you like, look for the style next time you are shopping.

Here are the styles:

– Wedge Shoes and Sandals. Many people tell us that wedges are more comfortable than heels. And wedge sandals are becoming very popular now. So if you like heels, because they make you look taller, but can't wear high heeled shoes, because they are not comfortable, check out wedges. When we looked, we found lots of very cool looking [\[link\]](#) wedge shoes – with embellishments, in many different colors and more.

– Platform Shoes and Sandals. Yes, you heard it right – platform shoes are back in style. Choose from different styles and heights. From a full platform to a platform heel to a tiny platform, we have seen many different platform shoes online and in stores.

– Metallic Shoes. Gold, silver and platinum don't describe just jewelry anymore. Now there are many cool sandals in all of the metal colors. They are really fun, and they will go with dressy clothing, and they will dress up a simple outfit of jeans and a top.

Check out metallic colored shoes – if they fit with the rest of your things, you will look cool in them.

– High Heeled Shoes and Sandals. If you love high heeled sandals, they have been around for a while, and they don't go out of style. They can dress up your jeans, and they will look great with a skirt and top or a dress.



– Low Heeled Shoes and Sandals. There are many people who don't like, or can't wear high heels. Low heels are in style now, so there are lots of shoes with small heels by all of your favorite shoe designers. Check them out, you will be able to find a pair of shoes that you like and would want to wear.

Get a cool new pair of shoes to celebrate a new season!